

Cinema and Intellectual Property Concept.

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Photography, one of the traditional visual art media transformed into motion or live visual art medium, was not just a technological change. Some of the earliest motion pictures produced by the Lumiere brothers in 1895, and some of the primary motion pictures made by Thomas Alva Edison, can be traced back to the beginning of World Cinema and were merely a series of moving images.

Thus, Cinema became the seventh art medium in the world. The human ability to invent and create different things is limitless. That ability occurs due to the constant curiosity in man. The interest in experimenting with ideas and technology about everything gives various innovations and designs.

This concept of intellectual property was born to provide an accurate value to the creations and inventions being created and provide value to those creators

economically, socially, and culturally. From the beginning of Cinema to the present, man has been experimenting and producing films. However, creators have to bear a considerable cost for these innovations in the present. Therefore, the concept of intellectual property, which is an essential concept in the field of Law to give economic value to those creations and protect the creators, should be applied to Cinema. In broad consideration, intellectual property is 'The legal protection of works that arise as a result of intelligence-driven activities in the fields of economics, science, industry, literature, and the arts (Botheju, 2013, p. 13). Intellectual property is mainly divided into two parts.

1. Industrial property
2. Copyright

Manufactured creations have got a broader definition with the advent of copyright law. Copyright is a legal right recognized by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights to protect artistic designs.

Literature, scientific and artistic works fall under the publication copyright category without considering the published method. This process protects the rights of the person doing the creation. Audio-visual creations such as novels, short stories, screenplays, music, movies, and telenovels are also included in these artistic works and can be copyrighted accordingly. These cultural creations give copyright to people who have made it their livelihood to secure their economy. Therefore, it should protect their legal rights. Copyright, one of the two types of intellectual property, is a type of property that has economic value. Any work cannot be used commercially without the author's permission because it is an economically valuable property. Accordingly, the author's copyright is fully protected. The owner can use their discretion under copyright law, but this should not affect the rights of others.

Consumption of Defensive Publication.

The prevailing copyright law in Sri Lanka is the Intellectual Property Act No. 36 of 2003; sections 6 and 7 of chapter 1, part II of the Act provides for protected works by the publication Act when creative work is protected by copyright for a limited period; it is called a defence work. Subsection (e) of this sixth amendment also protects audio-visual works. Audio-visual work means,

A work that consists of a series of related images which impart the impression of motion, with or without accompanying sounds, susceptible of being made visible, and were accompanied by sounds susceptible of being audible (Intellectual Property Act No. 36 of 2003, 2003, ch. I, p. 3).

Accordingly, any film can be considered as an audio-visual work. Further, the provisions covering subsections (a) to subsection (l) of section 6 of the Act are specified. Section 7 also protects other works based on original work. Such works as films based on a novel are called derivative works. Because of the Intellectual Property Act No.36 of 2003, Article 6 of the Act also protects publications on the internet. As a result, the Act protects films uploaded to social media sites like YouTube.

This Act also provides copyright protection to the original owners of online publications. All rights are reserved for the creation without considering the publication's content and quality. Registration is never required to obtain copyright for such works, and the author copyrights them from the moment a work is created.

Sri Lankan Law requires the use of such copyright to obtain permission from the copyright holder. However, an amendment to the intellectual property (Amendment) Act No.8 of 2021 empowers the Minister in charge of the subject to authorize specific organizations to compile works that are visually impaired or accessible to persons who are unable to grasp a visual work (Liyanaarachchi, 2021, p. 23).

However, it is not legal to reproduce a film without permission. In such a case, the work's original owner can take legal action against the person who violated that Law under the publication Act.

Copyright and Economic Rights

Under these economic rights, the copyright holder has absolute rights over his work. Here he can make a financial profit by giving his creation to others for use under these economic rights, and he gets another set of rights.

A set of rights is obtained from 'subsection (a) to subsection (e) of section 9 of the Intellectual Property Act. Sub clauses contain a bundle of rights, such as the work's reproduction, sale, rent, or public performance. That set of rights is set out in the appendices of this book.

The copyright holder may control the work's copyright by agreeing with the publisher and the person and entity agreeing to claim the economic rights. Accordingly, the owner of any film is entitled to the above set of rights.

Copyright ownership and Validity period.

The creator holds the copyright from when an invention or creation is created. This process is a matter recognized by Law. Nevertheless, sometimes, the situation is different. For instance, a company owns the copyright on a design created by one of its employees working under contract for it, not the employee. However, the creator of this has a moral right without considering the owner of that institution or the institution. This idea is clear from the sub-clauses in section 10 of the intellectual property act No.36 of 2003.

Subsection (a) of Article 10 states that the name of the author of the work should be prominently displayed.

When discussing the period for which copyright exists, the rights associated with this copyright apply to a limited period. Accordingly, the economic and moral rights related to copyright are protected under Article 13 of the intellectual property act No.36 of 2003 for a lifetime and 70 years from the date of his death. Once the relevant period expires, the creation of the publication becomes public property. When it becomes public property, anyone or any institution can reproduce and use it. For example, some of Munidasa Kumaratunga's novels can now be made into films.

Fair Use

Local Law does not allow copyright to be used without the permission of the copyright holder. However, there are some exceptions to this in local Law. One of them is Fair Use. 'It is considered fair to copy a copyrighted work for non-commercial purposes without the publisher's permission' (Liyanaarachchi, 2021, P. 26).

According to article 11 of the intellectual property act, using a work for the following purposes is not a copyright infringement.

1. Criticism
2. Comment
3. News reporting
4. Teaching
5. For scholarships or research activities.

There are some facts to consider regarding whether it is fair use for particular reasons. It is set out in Article 11 (2).

- A) Whether that use is commercial or for a nonprofit educational purpose.
- B) The nature of the publication with copyright.

If any film is quoted for educational purposes, the place where it is mentioned and the name of the owner should be clearly stated.

Remedies for Copyright infringement.

Many of the issues regarding copyright in the film industry have arisen due to verbal agreements between the artist and various creators based on personal friendships. Unfortunately, friendships are shattered, and conflicts arise when people contribute to films based on oral agreements and reap the good economic benefits of those productions. The intellectual property Act No. 36 of 2003 sets out some remedies that can be taken in case of copyright in the filmmaking process, and legal action can be taken as follows;

1. Dispute Settlement

This dispute resolution is the practical procedure of the intellectual property Act No.36 of 2003. This fact is introduced in section 22 (3) of chapter II of part II of the Act. This conciliation process takes place at no charge. This conciliation program was published in the extraordinary Gazette Notification No. 1415/18 dated 19th October 2005. This gazette has been referred to as the Intellectual Property Order No. 1 of 2005 (Intellectual Property Order No. 1 of 2005, 2005).

According to these orders, the application should be submitted to the Director-General of Intellectual Property for

mediation of disputes within one month after discovering their rights have been violated. As mentioned in the gazette notification, this should be submitted as form C1. Two copies of the affidavit must also be submitted with any relevant facts on the disagreement, including any technical details. Upon receipt, the accused is directed to make submissions within a month. If the accused person does not appear before the Director-General or fails to respond, the Act allows for a unilateral decision. Section 22 (3) of chapter II, part II of the Intellectual Property Act No. 36 of 2003 is valid until the decision of the Director-General is stayed by a court of Law. Finally, a party dissatisfied with the decision can file an appeal with the Court of Appeal. It may be suggested that this first course of action be taken when a copyright issue arises during the filmmaking process because going to Court is a costly affair.

2. Acting Under Civil Law.

Chapter 38 of the intellectual property act No.36 of 2003 may apply to an injunction restraining an infringing action by the provincial High Court in the relevant area in the event of an infringement of copyright and related rights. In addition, other relief may be requested if deemed appropriate.

Former Judge A.C. Alles filed a copyright lawsuit against Wasantha Obesekara's film *Dadayama* in 1984. The book, *The Famous Criminal Cases of Sri Lanka*, is based on a true story by Alles. It was alleged that Wasantha Obesekara had infringed on his copyright by producing the film *Dadayama* (1984) based on unauthorized excerpts from his book. Accordingly, a case was filed against Mr. Obeysekara in the Mount Lavinia District Court, where Wasantha

Obesekara was found guilty of violating the copyright of Mr. Alles and was ordered to pay a compensation of Rs.200,000. Wasantha Obeysekara filed an appeal in the Court of Appeal under case No.730/92. This case is known as *Anthony Christopher Vs. Obeysekara*. The Court eventually acquitted Wasantha Obeysekara of Appeal

Accordingly, a party who infringes his copyright in filmmaking can obtain remedies under civil Law.

3. Acting under Criminal Law

Anyone who infringes on this copyright may be prosecuted under criminal Law. For example, a person who intentionally violates the security rights of publication

commits a criminal offence. The aggrieved party can file a case against such a person in the magistrate court. If convicted, section 178 of the Intellectual Property Act No. 36 of 2003 carries a fine of less than Rs. 500,000 or imprisonment not exceeding six months or both.

Section 178 (4) of the Act destroys copies and allows the equipment used to reproduce them to be acted upon as appropriate by the Magistrate. Further, infringing on this copyright is a signal offence that a police officer can be arrested without a warrant. Accordingly, it should be clarified that this should not be violated as it is a criminal offence punishable by severe penalties.

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